

YEAR: 2024

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL TM

**A QUARTERLY MULTIDISCIPLINARY BLIND PEER REVIEWED
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ISSN: 3048-7951

This is certified that the Paper Title “Impact of Out-Migration on Rural Households; A Theoretical Study” authored by “Rajat Raj” has been published in the Volume-(2) Issue-(2) May-July 2025, ADEJ with PIF:1.024 with plagiarism free through rigorous blind peer review process in term of originality and quality of work by review committee of ADEJ.

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Google Scholar

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AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL TM

ISSN: 3048-7951

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& REFEREED ONLINE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

This is certified that the Paper Title “Impact of Out-Migration on Rural Households; A Theoretical Study” authored by “Dr. Subal Tandi” has been published in the Volume-(2) Issue-(2) May-July 2025, ADEJ with PIF:1.024 with plagiarism free through rigorous blind peer review process in term of originality and quality of work by review committee of ADEJ.

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